

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STRESS DISORDER AND ITS COMPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, mainly unfavorable changes are observed in the mental health of the population. There is a significant increase in the number of neuropsychiatric diseases, especially those that are the most characteristic reaction to mental stress. These are primarily neuroses, post-traumatic stress disorders, psychosomatic disorders, characterological and pathocharacterological reactions, as well as reactive psychoses, and others are considered.

Today, stress specialists use relatively new terms for mental disorders that occur in adverse social conditions: information neuroses, generalized anxiety disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, diseases of victims of military stress, disasters, etc. (Хохлов Л.К., Шипов А.А., Горохов В.И., 2003)

Differences between research on stress and traumatic stress are methodological in nature. Thus, most research on traumatic stress has focused on assessing the relationship between trauma and the disorders it causes, as well as assessing the degree of traumatic events.

Traumatic stress is a special form of general stress response. Referring to the literature, when the concept of stress is explained, it is explained as the anxiety that occurs when a person's psychological, physiological, adaptation capabilities are overloaded.

Keywords: stress disorder, posttraumatic stress disorder, complication of stress, stress disorder levels.

In the 19th century, Emil Kraepelin used the term *schreckneurosis* ("fire neurosis") to designate a distinct clinical condition involving multiple nervous and physical phenomena caused by various emotional shocks or sudden fear that turns into anxiety. This condition was observed after severe accidents, especially fires, railway accidents or collisions.

J.Erichen observed a similar reaction to traumatic events in England in 1882. J.Erichen, who described such reactions after the railway accident, as a supporter of the anatomical direction, suggested that the syndrome was caused by molecular changes in the spinal cord (Тарабрина Н.В., 2008). Not everyone agreed with him, suggesting that there are psychological reasons as well as physical damage. As a result, the term "traumatic neurosis" appeared to diagnose mental disorders in combatants, the causes of which were seen in organic brain disorders caused by both physical and psychological factors.

In 1889, X. Oppenheim applied the term "traumatic neurosis" to the diagnosis of mental disorders in combatants, which he saw as brain disorders caused by both physical and psychological factors. Many observations of psychopathological conditions after participation in military operations were made during the First World War.

I. Bekhterev, P. Gannushkin, F. Zarubin, S. Kraits, and after the Great Patriotic War - E. Krasnushkin, V. Gilyarovskiy, A. Arkhangelsky and many other researchers dealt with the psychological and other problems of the participants of the First World War. After World War I, there remained extensive documentation of the neurological and psychological effects of war trauma. Separate descriptions of the consequences of military stress experienced by soldiers have even been published, which include obsessive repetition of life-threatening situations, as well as increased irritability,

reactions to loud noises, difficulty concentrating, etc. the data are recorded (Тарабрина Н.В.,2008).

In the 1980s, research on PTSD expanded further. Numerous studies have been conducted in the United States to develop and clarify various aspects of PTSD. Among them, I would like to mention the works of A. Egendorf and others, as well as G. Boulanger and others (Тарабрина Н.В.,2008).The first of them is a comparative analysis of the characteristics of the adaptation process in Vietnam veterans and their non-combatant peers, and the second is to study the characteristics of their delayed response to stress. The results of these studies have not lost their importance until now. The main results of the international research are summarized in the collective two-volume monograph "Trauma and its traces", which, in addition to the developmental characteristics of PTSD of military etiology, also reflect the results of the study of stress effects in victims of genocide, other tragic events or personal violence.

In 1988, data from a nationwide retest study on various aspects of postwar adaptation of Vietnam War veterans were also published. These studies have made it possible to clarify many issues related to the nature and diagnosis of PTSD.

In parallel with the social phenomena that developed throughout the 20th century, the physical and mental effects of trauma continued to be the subject of research. After the devastation caused by the First World War, S. Freud began to work on this topic again and in the articles "The Pleasure Principle" (1920) and "Psychoanalysis of War Neurosis" (1919) defined one of the main symptom groups of the psychological trauma that we know as re-experiencing with the definition of "repetitive compulsion" (Freud, S.,1915/1957). During this period, British psychologist Charles Myers used the term "bomb shock" based on his symptomatic findings (Herman, J. L.,2007). Alt-

though bomb shock was originally understood as physical destruction, over time, the frequent appearance of similar symptoms in soldiers not exposed to bombs has led to the recognition of bomb shock as a symptom cluster associated with psychological trauma (Herman, J. L., 2007).

After the First World War, A. Kardiner began to work with war veterans and, as a result of these studies, was the first to define "Traumatic neurosis". In 1941, A. Kardiner defined the main criteria of traumatic neurosis in his book "Traumatic neuroses", which includes the results of his clinical and theoretical researches, and noted that war survivors often suffer from traumatic amnesia (Kardiner, A., 1941).

The results of the two world wars of the 20th century forced the American public to officially recognize the problem of psycho-traumatic consequences of military operations, and in 1952 the title "reaction to severe emotional and physical stress" was included in the DSM-II, but already in 1968 this diagnosis was removed from the classification. After the Vietnam War, the category of "traumatic stress disorder" appears in DSM-III with the following criteria: re-experiencing, avoidance, emotional impoverishment, and physiological arousal.

After World War II, works devoted to the study of consequences of the war. The delayed effects of being in concentration camps have been reflected in many publications. In addition to malnutrition and disease, these people were subjected to forced labor, beatings and more complex torture. Almost 23% of those surveyed suffered from war-related nightmares and fears, blunted affect, memory loss, severe irritability and depression. 100 Norwegian prisoners of Nazi camps were examined and it was found that 85 of them had chronic fatigue, reduced ability to concentrate and acute irritability.

Thus, the debate between the organic and psychological approach to the state, defined by various authors, continued until the end of World War II, after which the psychological direction prevailed. In general, the symptoms indicated by A. Kardiner remained in later studies, although the nature and mechanisms of the impact of war factors on a person, especially as a result of the study of the problems associated with the Vietnam War, were significantly expanded.

Post-traumatic stress disorder is an illness that some people develop after experiencing a shocking, frightening or dangerous life event. Psychological aspects of experiencing post-traumatic stress and its consequences are usually studied in the context of general problems of human activity in extreme conditions, human adaptation possibilities and stress tolerance. The results of such studies focus on the social, natural, technological, individual psychological, ecological and medical aspects of human existence in the modern world.

According to H. Selye, stress is a non-specific reaction of the body to any change in conditions that requires adaptation (Селье Г., 1960). Some of the famous researchers of stress, such as R. Lazarus, followers of H. Selye, as a possible consequence of stress, like other

disorders, mainly ignore PTSD, limiting the focus of research on the characteristics of emotional stress (Lazarus R. 1966).

The phenomenology of posttraumatic stress is described in the work of N. V. Tarabrina. According to the author, the psychological consequences of a long or delayed reaction to situations characterized by an extraordinary impact on the human psyche, which create traumatic stress in it, are associated with a serious threat to life or health, arise as situations expressed in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in its extreme manifestation (Тарабрина Н.В., 2008).

According to the ICD-10, PTSD includes the following symptoms:

- intrusive memories, thoughts and nightmares related to the traumatic event;
- regular experience of emotions accompanying a traumatic event, when remembering or relating to it;
- avoiding memories and situations that remind of the traumatic situation;
- psychogenic amnesia at the time of psychotrauma;
- sleep problems, irritability, hypersensitivity;
- cognitive functions are disturbed (first of all attention sphere violations).

According to literature review and previous studies, it should be noted that initial psychological help and specialized help are important in overcoming post-traumatic stress disorder. At this time, the initial psychological help should be aimed at reducing the distress related to the traumatic event and meeting the basic needs such as comfort, information, practical and emotional support. Primary psychological help is carried out in order to increase a person's resistance to stressful situations and to fight trauma. However, if the impossibility of achieving the desired result is registered in the conditions of primary medical care, specialized assistance should be provided. Specialized assistance is provided by using medicine and non-drug treatment methods.

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